

Recommendation 13:

Using 'API Economy' to meet the societal need 'Faster and transparent access to PS services'

Status quo:

Today, APIs play a central role in integrating companies with providers, suppliers and customers.

API economy related to PS services refers mainly to the public sector itself releasing open data which in turn can be consumed by businesses through APIs to provide value to citizens and potentially earn some revenue.

Everyday uses of this can be businesses that want to access traffic data to find opportunities for marketing (e.g. to people stuck in traffic). Infrastructure planning and zoning are also potential consumers of this data. Population and census data can be made available via APIs for outside developers to access and use in their Apps in creative ways.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Expansion of critical channels that need to be protected
- Deploy real-time analytics broadly, by moving analytics to the data
- Ancillary components required: documentation, code samples, testing and certification tools, support models, monitoring, maintenance, and upkeep

Non-technical challenges:

- '*data first*' approach to unlock all data from current applications in the PS.
- *Marketplace*: Create a data marketplace where different creators and consumers of data can buy, sell, request or freely exchange data
- *Privacy and security concerns* arise whenever public sector entities share data, especially citizen data.
- *Data ownership and liability*, regardless of whether the APIs are open or protected.
- *Processes*: Creating the API economy in the public sector will require executive-level leadership and governance. PS leaders will need to champion API initiatives in order to overcome organizational inertia.

Faster and transparent access to PS services:

The sub needs under this header include: trust in governance, access to timely and accurate information, unlink Public Sector and politics.

The time frame in which the public sector is required to respond tends to shorten to meet government imperatives and citizen and stakeholder demands. A transparent public sector is an essential element of a free and democratic society. Information from a wide variety of sources must be accessed and presented to citizens in an intuitive, easy to use fashion. In addition, the public sector should strive to provide an easy way for citizens to retrieve a wide variety of documents.

Our informants said: "Public Authorities already know my social situation, why should I investigate the social benefits I am entitled to? Make citizen's life easier"

API Economy:

*The API Economy refers to the trend of turning a business or organization into a platform by using Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) to integrate and connect people, places, systems, data, things and algorithms, create new user experiences, share data and information, authenticate people and things, enable transactions and algorithms, leverage third-party algorithms, and create new product/services and business models, thus positively affecting the organization's profitability**

* Smarter with Gartner, Welcome to the API Economy, <http://www.gartner.com/smarterwithgartner/welcome-to-the-api-economy/>